

EXPERIMENTAL FLOW-FRONT VISUALISATION IN COMPRESSION MOULDING OF SMC

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ABSTRACT

This work is primarily focused on experimental visualisation of the flow during mould closure in compression moulding of sheet moulding compound (SMC). Circular plates are manufactured with industry scale equipment at close to production conditions. Special attention is given to the advancing flow front, for which the full complexity is captured by means of continuous high resolution close-up monitoring. From the experimental visualisation of the flow front, three phases are defined, namely pitch, floating, and boiling. During the initial phase, pitch, outer layers do not remain outer layers, the actual flow is very complex and air is likely to be entrapped. The governing process parameters during this phase are mould temperature, mould closing speed and amount of preheating in the mould. During the second phase, floating, the flow is stable and seemingly viscous. During the last phase, boiling, bubbles are observed in the low pressure region at the flow front, favouring the void content both internally and on the surface. Based on a chemical analysis including mass spectrometry and thermogravimetry, the gas is probably styrene. Finally a qualitative investigation of the surface quality of the moulded plates is carried out. It is observed that the surface void is reduced with an increased mould temperature and that the mould closing speed does not seem to have any influence on the surface quality at lower mould temperatures while at higher mould temperatures, an increased mould closing speed clearly gives a reduction of surface void

INTRODUCTION

In manufacturing of composites, design practice and appropriate process development are key issues. Important characteristics are i) cost effectiveness, which mainly depends on high production rate, and ii) reliability, which stands for a maintained quality level. In applications where a high production rate in long series is prioritised rather than high strength, methods like compression moulding are being emphasized. One such method is compression moulding of Sheet Moulding Compound (SMC), where the SMC is a continuous sheet containing chopped fibres and mineral fillers embedded in a highly viscous thermosetting resin. Compression moulding is also used for bulk moulding compounds (BMC) and glass mat thermoplastics (GMT). The ability to include complex geometry, such as ribs, flanges and holes eliminates a number of secondary finishing operations and has made compression moulding one of the most important methods for manufacturing of many high volume automotive components. The automotive industries have high demands on tolerance and surface finish, with a class A surfaces being a surface with very little defects when painted.

The general procedure in compression moulding of SMC is as follows. First, plies of SMC are cut to a desired shape and size and stacked outside the preheated mould to form a charge. The charge is then placed on the lower mould half and the movable upper mould half is brought down to close the mould. As the mould pressure builds up, the SMC is forced towards the outer edges of the cavity. Once the mould is adequately filled, the mould pressure is kept during a preset time, i.e. until a predetermined degree of curing in the moulded part is achieved. The top mould half is then brought back up and the part is removed from the mould for cooling and post mould curing. Now, regardless of the manufacturing method, the flow of resin impregnating the fibres, or in some cases, the flow of already impregnated fibres, is in general a very complex process. Furthermore, it is by far the most important factor in determining the quality of the moulded part, affecting everything from fibres distribution and orientation to void content and surface defects. A fundamental understanding of the flow process, the mechanism and its relations to the process parameters, is therefore essential in order to ensure optimum and secure processing.

In the late 1970's Marker and Ford [1] performed a pioneering work on visualisation of the filling of the mould by multicoloured charges. This method was later adapted by Barone and Caulk [2], who in 1985 performed partial mouldings by insertion of steel shims between the mould stops. Both layered and segmented charges were used and the stages of deformation were examined in sections cut from the cured parts. The same year, 1985, Costigan, Fisher and Kanagendra [3], presented flow front studies using both the partial moulding technique with multicoloured layers and also video recording and photographing of the flow front in a mould with the sides removed. The partial moulding technique was however discarded since it, according to the authors, failed to capture the true flow front. Instead, Kanagendra and Fischer [4] presented schematic drawings based on the video records and photographs of the flow front. Then, in 1986 Barone and Caulk [5] proposed a mathematical model based on their earlier observations [2], with several different validated alternatives for the boundary conditions at the mould surfaces. This is the starting point of a period where focus is changing from experimental visualisation to development of mathematical models and numerical simulations, cf. [6, 7, 8] Eventually, in 1994 this trend led Tucker and Advani [9] to recognise the then current models as adequate analysis tools for predictions of microstructure and composite properties. However, they stated that one of the major research challenges is to contrive good ways to use these models as design tools, rather than for diagnosis, i.e. to determine mould geometry, material properties and processing conditions based on the desired part properties.

The work in this report is primarily focused on experimental visualisation of the flow during mould closure. Hence we aim at continuing the work that was postponed during the late 1980's. Special attention is given to the advancing flow front, for which the full complexity is captured by means of continuous high resolution close-up monitoring. Early we discovered that the visualisation could be divided into three different phases. For simplicity we defined them as *Pitch*, *Floating* and *Boiling*, making it easy for everyone to follow the course of events. Furthermore, in order to qualify and quantify certain gaseous emissions from the SMC, a chemical analysis including mass spectrometry and thermogravimetry is performed. Finally an examination of the final surface quality based on the amount and distribution of surface void is carried out.

EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP AND PROCEDURE

The outline of this section follows the course of events as they evolved during the experiments. First the used material and moulding equipment will be described. Then the strategy and equipment for the visualisation of the advancing flow front, which is the

main focus of this report, is treated. Last a brief summary of the apparatus used in the chemical analysis of gaseous emissions is given. All experiments were performed on industry scaled equipment at close to production conditions and the experimental procedure is as follows.

The material used in this study is a standard SMC with industrial applications. The continuous sheets contain chopped strands of Vetrotex E-glass (average length 26 mm) from a 4800 roving with a 1,25 % size embedded in an isophthalic-based polyester. Magnesium oxide (MgO) is added to the resin paste as thickener, polystyrene as low shrink additive, CaCO₃ as filler and a zinc stearate as mould release agent. The viscosity of the unprocessed SMC was measured continuously during the experiments and was found to be approximately 40 Pas. Circular samples of the SMC were cut out using a sharp blade knife and a rigid template with a diameter of 100 millimetres. The circular shape was chosen in order to minimise effects of anisotropy and to maximise the visibility of the flow front. Each sample was taken randomly from the continuous sheet and the same cutting technique was used throughout the experimental series. Five samples were carefully stacked on top of each other to form a charge. Each charge was weighed straight after being put together (160 ± 2 g) and only fresh cut samples were used in order to maintain similar initial material properties. A charge was then placed centrally between two parallel and circular plates ($\varnothing = 300$ mm) mounted in a 310 tonnes Fjellman hydraulic press. In order to ensure a high repeatability and to facilitate handling, the exact charge position was indicated with a marker directly on the lower mould half. Of practical reasons, 2 mm distances were used. An entire tool surface renovation was performed before the experiments were started in order to obtain well defined in mould flow conditions and to avoid disturbances of the flow front. Also, because of the high surface finish, no additional mould lubricant was needed. The interpretation of the results, such as anisotropy of the charge and final surface evaluation was thereby simplified. In addition, the sides of the tools were painted matt black to avoid optical reflections.

The process parameters that were altered are the mould temperatures of the lower and upper tool and the mould closing speed. Three different mould temperature combinations were evaluated. *First*, a uniform temperature of 135 °C was used on the lower surface as on the upper mould half. *Second*, the temperature of the upper mould half was raised to 165 °C while keeping the lower mould at 135 °C. *Third* and last, again a uniform temperature was used, this time 165 °C. For each temperature case, two different mould closing speeds were applied, 2 and 15 mm/s. The in-mould cure time was set to 180 seconds and held constant throughout the experiments. The hydraulic pressure force was set high enough (approximately 600kN) to prevent the tools from separating during curing of the SMC.

For high-resolution close-ups, a Panasonic F15HS video camera was used. The camera was mounted on a fully adjustable tripod and equipped with a 135 mm 1:2 Nikon objective and two spacers (K3 and K5). A small torch with a narrow beam provided proper illumination. Since the camera has no means of internal storage, all video was transferred to a Panasonic NV-FS200 EC S-VHS recorder. Digitised versions of the video recordings were obtained with aid of a Pinnacle DC1000 combined with appropriate software. Individual frames could then be extracted with a sampling frequency of 25 frames per second and a resolution of 720 x 576 pixels. The horizontal and vertical extent of the field of view is with this set-up approximately 31 and 17 millimetres respectively. Based on the geometry of the mould, a side view of the advancing flow front was chosen. Once the upper mould half reaches the top layer, the SMC will deform and the flow will be from left to right. Due to the limited width of the field of view, the whole flow distance could not be covered at once. Instead the camera set-up was translated in a direction parallel to the movement of the flow front. In this manner the total flow distance was covered in three steps. In addition the overall development was captured by a

supplementary video camera with a field of view approximately 100 millimetres wide, ensuring the global overview.

During the experimental work substantial gaseous emissions from the SMC were observed. In order to clarify the contents of these emissions, an investigation with a mass spectrometry system was carried out. The basic principle of a mass spectrometry system is detection and identification of ionised molecules. While the mass spectrometry system gives a qualitative measure of the contents of the gaseous emissions, a quantitative measure is given by running a thermogravimetry system in parallel. In this way the weight reduction is monitored and correlated to the gas contents. In the analysis performed the mass spectrometry equipment is a Quadropole mass spectrometer system from Balzer Instruments and the thermogravimetry is performed with a Netzsch STA409.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

We shall here start with the visualisation of the flow front, where the first main result is that the flow process during mould closing in compression moulding of SMC can be divided into three phases, namely *pitch*, *floating* and *boiling*. Each one of these three phases will now be explained and dealt with separately, followed by a chemical analysis of certain gaseous emissions from the SMC. Finally, a qualitative examination of the final shape and surface quality of the moulded parts is given. As far as possible, this section is restricted to experimental observations, leaving interpretation and discussion to the next section.

During the initial moments of contact, as the upper mould half reaches the top surface of the charge, the first phase, *pitch*, is defined as the first squirt of paste emerging from the charge as the moulding pressure is building up. For a high mould closing speed (15 mm/s) and a rather low mould temperature (135 °C), the bottom layer yields to the pressure first and hits the upper mould half (before the top layers even start to deform), cf. Figure 1, where the elapsed time between each frame is 0.04 seconds. An increased mould temperature to 165 °C does not affect the manner of the pitch, as long as the mould closing speed is kept constant at 15 mm/s. The pattern shown in Figure 1 is thus preserved, though with an augmented intensity.

Figure 1. Mould closing speed 15 mm/s, uniform mould temperature 135 °C and elapsed time between each frame 0.04 seconds.

At lower mould closing speeds however, there is an effect on the pattern when the mould temperature is increased. With a uniform mould temperature of 135 °C and a mould closing speed of 2 mm/s, the bottom layer leaves the charge first. Now, if the upper mould temperature is increased to 165 °C and everything else is held constant, then also the top layer shoots out to meet the bottom layer, before the other layers start to deform, cf. Figure 2. Note that the elapsed time between each frame here is 0.32 seconds.

Figure 2. Mould closing speed 2 mm/s, lower mould half temperature 135 °C, upper mould half temperature 165 °C and elapsed time between each frame 0.32 seconds.

After the initial tumultuous phase, *pitch*, the flow front settles down in a seemingly stable and viscous flow, here defined as *floating*, cf. the last frames of Figure 1. Any debris, such as loose fibre ends produced by the pitch when using a lower mould closing speed, is simply pushed ahead of the flow front and later on easily identified along the edges of the final plates.

During closure of the mould, before complete cross-linking of the resin, bubbles are observed emerging from the resin in the low-pressure region (atmospheric pressure) at the flow front: it appears as if the resin is *boiling*. Figure 3 shows the boiling near the flow front in a mould temperature of 135 °C, and in Figure 4 the mould temperature is 165 °C. Observations made from the video recordings indicate that the bubbles are larger for the higher temperature while the number of bubbles is greater in the lower temperature, cf. Figure 3 and Figure 4. Also, from the elapsed time between each frame, which is 3.00 seconds in Figure 3 and 0.08 seconds in Figure 4, it is clear that the outbursts last longer in the lower temperature case than in the higher temperature ditto. The difference in size of the bubbles is also confirmed by examination of the final edges of the moulded parts. Still, the mere existence, and certainly the origin of the bubbles are as intriguing as their physical appearance. This matter is now to be dealt with.

Figure 3. Mould closing speed 15 mm/s, uniform mould temperature 135 °C and elapsed time between each frame 3.00 seconds.

Figure 4. Mould closing speed 15 mm/s, uniform mould temperature 165 °C and elapsed time between each frame 0.08 seconds.

In order to identify the contents of gaseous emissions during conditions similar to the boiling of the resin, a chemical analysis was performed. First a 216.0 mg sample of SMC was placed in a heated oven (135 °C) during 10 minutes under atmospheric pressure. The weight afterwards was 203.1 mg, i.e. a 5.6% weight reduction. In the same manner the weight reduction was 4.5% when a 222.9 mg sample was subjected to a temperature of 165 °C for 10 minutes. The emitted gases were meanwhile collected and analysed in the mass spectrometry system. The ionisation spectra from empty reference samples subjected to the same conditions were then subtracted from the obtained spectra for each temperature in order to avoid possible background noise. In both temperature cases, the final ionisation spectrum matched perfectly the ionisation spectrum of styrene. Thus, the ultimate outcome of importance is that everything else but styrene could be dismissed, not originating from the samples of SMC.

Finally, the moulded plates were examined in two steps. First, the surface quality on each side was evaluated based on the overall amount of surface void. Three levels were used: poor, intermediate or good. Second, the geometric distribution of surface void was determined. Here only two levels were needed: circumferential or uniform distribution. Both steps were repeated independently to ensure objectivity.

One general observation of this qualitative investigation is that the amount of surface void is reduced with an increased mould temperature, see Table 1. Another observation is that the mould closing speed does not seem to have any influence on the surface quality at lower mould temperatures. At higher temperatures, an increased mould closing speed clearly gives a reduction of surface void, cf. Table 1. Considering the geometrical shape of the plates manufactured in the higher temperature case (165 °C), there is a striking difference in final volume (approximately 20 %) of a plate manufactured with a low mould closing speed (2 mm/s) as compared to the final volume of a plate manufactured with a higher mould closing speed (15 mm/s).

Table 1. Surface quality and surface void distribution for moulded plates

Mould temp. (°C)		Mould closing speed (mm/s)	Surface quality		Surface void distribution	
Lower	Upper		Lower	Upper	Lower	Upper
135	135	2	intermediate	poor	circumference	uniform
135	135	15	intermediate	poor	uniform	uniform
135	165	2	intermediate	intermediate	uniform	circumference
135	165	15	poor	good	uniform	circumference
165	165	2	intermediate	intermediate	circumference	circumference
165	165	15	good	good	circumference	circumference

DISCUSSION

The visualisation demonstrated that during the initial phase, the *pitch*, the SMC close to the lower mould half can move considerably faster towards the edges than the SMC in the rest of the charge. The obvious explanation to this is two folded: First of all, the charge is placed on a heated mould half before pressing and the material close to this mould half gets the lowest viscosity. Secondly, at pressing, the time in contact with the upper mould half is not long enough to obtain a symmetric flow. The latter was however achieved by an increased temperature of the upper mould half, see Figure 2. In any case, during the initial stage of the pressing the flow is complex with an almost certain entrapment of air. Similar phenomena has been observed in connection to injection moulding processes such as RTM and the best solution to minimize the void content is to evacuate the mould before and after pressing [10]. An alternative route is to preheat the charge or adjust the pressing speed or/and the temperature on the mould halves. The latter was tested in this study, as explained above, but did only change the pattern of the *pitch* and air seemed to be enclosed in all cases. Another consequence of the *pitch*, worthwhile mentioning, is that the flow front will probably consist of the SMC that has been heated the longest time. This is likely to be important for the subsequent curing.

In the next phase, *floating*, the flow front was observed to settle down in a stable and seemingly viscous flow, probably due to a more evenly distributed viscosity. There is therefore no indication on void entrapment during this stage as long as the geometry of the mould is simple enough. However, as a consequence of the stability it was observed that disorders created during the *pitch*, e.g. fibre entanglement at the flow front, are preserved during *floating*. Such effects may make it difficult to directly fill geometries such as ribs and bosses and hence air will be entrapped. It may also influence the final fibre orientation distribution [11].

In the last phase, *boiling*, bubbles were observed emerging from the resin in the low-pressure region at the flow front and chemical analysis indicated boiling of styrene. Regardless of the contents of the bubbles, they are without doubt an important source of void, both internally and on the surface. By inspection of the moulded plates it was, for instance, observed that all plates had surface voids in an area close to the edges, see Table 1. It is therefore important to keep the overall pressure on the SMC higher than the pressure corresponding to the boiling point at the prevailing temperature [10].

Other differences in surface void content presented in Table 1, are at this stage difficult to interpret. One speculation is that the difference in quality is due to time and spatial variations in solidification, in combination with effects of the *pitch*.

In order to model the shape of the flow front it seems crucial to identify the viscosity as a function of time. The most intuitive route to this end would be to control the material

parameters influencing the viscosity and the effect from the processing conditions. If even possible, this route would demand many time consuming measurements. An alternative, and possibly more successful route to this end would be a kind of inverse modelling where simulations are fitted to experiments by adjustment of suitable material parameters, leaving the viscosity as the last dependent variable to be monitored. This is certainly a topic of burning hot interest for future work.

CONCLUSIONS

- From the experimental visualisation of the flow front, three phases are defined, namely *pitch*, *floating*, and *boiling*.
- During the initial phase, *pitch*:
 - the flow is very complex and air is likely to be entrapped
 - outer layers do not remain outer layers
 - the governing process parameters are mould temperature, mould closing speed and amount of preheating in the mould
- During the second phase, *floating*:
 - the flow is stable and seemingly viscous
 - there is no indication of void entrapment for the simple geometry in focus
- During the last phase, *boiling*:
 - bubbles are observed in the low pressure region at the flow front
 - the bubbles favour the void content, internally and on the surface
 - based on a chemical analysis, the gas is probably styrene
- From a qualitative investigation of the final surface quality of the moulded parts, the following conclusions were made:
 - the surface void is reduced with an increased mould temperature
 - the mould closing speed does not seem to have any influence on the surface quality at lower mould temperatures
 - at higher temperatures, an increased mould closing speed clearly gives a reduction of surface void

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